

Involvement of SDCA students in cyberbullying: Measures of counseling intervention among millennials

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Abstract

The research focuses on the involvement of students in cyberbullying as perpetrator as most students use social media to communicate with other people. The study also distinguished if there was a trend in various demographic variables which were age, gender, hours of online engagement, and type of student, either senior high school or college. The study is a descriptive quantitative to explain the statistics of the research. The study shows that there is a low involvement with the participants but still participate nonetheless, there is also a trend that the more they spend their hours online, the higher they get more involve or participate in cyberbullying rituals.

Keywords: *Involvement, SDCA students, cyberbullying, counseling intervention, millennials.*

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Introduction

The Philippines is the number one country in the world that spends the most time on the internet and in which Filipinos spend an average of 10 hours and two minutes daily via any device (Kemp, 2019). This exposure of Filipino adolescents established a potential adverse dynamic for social connections, one that has subsequently been called "online harassment" or "cyberbullying." Cyberbullying, also known as online harassment, is when someone uses information and communication technology (ICT) to harm another person. It might include sending harassing messages, making derogatory comments, publishing humiliating photographs, or intimidating and threatening someone (Moreno, 2014).

Because of the widespread use of the internet, cyberbullying perpetrators can remain anonymous and untraceable, and the posts or comments that they send or place are virtually impossible to delete or stop, especially if they are shared or passed around by others on social media, distributed across multiple sites, or saved on electronic devices (Zuckerman, 2016). Bullying, in both the traditional and online forms, does not only affect the mental and emotional health of the victim but of the perpetrators as well because in the long-term consequences it can lead to committing suicide, alcohol and drug abuse, early engagement in sexual activity, school drop-out, criminal convictions, and abuse to their romantic partners, spouses or their children as adults (Holt et al., 2015; Calloway & Paskewich, 2019). Identifying the perpetrator of online bullying is the objective of this study, as cyberbullies are difficult to be identified as they know

that they had been doing is wrong and they would go to great lengths to hide their involvement as they might ask for additional privacy or become totally anonymous in social media (Preston, 2015).

Methods

In this study, the researchers used the phenomenological method of descriptive and quantitative research. This study examined the relationship between variables and their levels of involvement in cyberbullying and in their academic achievement and self-esteem at their grade level. Survey questionnaires were administered to the respondents which consisted of two (2) parts of the test – one for the demographic questions and the second is a Likert scale for the rating of the involvement of cyberbullying. The sample respondents were chosen through a purposive sampling because of the current situation when the research was made. There are 156 cases gathered which comprises of 43 senior high school students and 113 college students.

According to Cristobal (2013), it is a method of sampling from a population which can be partitioned into subpopulations. The researchers categorized the respondents into the following categories: first, senior high school tracks which are Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics strand (STEM), General Academic strand (GA), Sports strand (S), Fitness and Recreational Leadership strand (FRL), Performing Arts strand (PA), Visual Art strand (VA), Information and Communications Technology strand (ICT), and Home Economics strand (HE); and for the college programs are Bachelor in Science in Accountancy, BS in Business Administration, Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Secondary Education, BS in Cruise Line Management, BS in Hospitality Management, BS in Hospitality Management major in Culinary Arts and Kitchen Operations, BS in Tourism Management, BS in Medical Technology, BS in Nursing, BS in Pharmacy, BS in Physical Therapy, Bachelor of Arts in Communication, BA in Multimedia Arts, BS in Information Technology, BS in Biology, and BS Psychology.

The research locale is in the home country of the researchers. The respondents were asked to answer using online forms as given by the researchers with the use of Google Forms. Due to the circumstances of the current situation when the research was written, the survey cannot be disseminated in person, the researchers took advantage of the use of Google Forms.

There were two (2) instruments used in this study, which are the qualitative and quantitative tests. These tests were self-made questionnaires. Respondents are all students with ages ranging from 18 to 25 years old. They are all senior high school and college students from different colleges and universities that are officially enrolled for this semester. The participants are willing to participate on the said research study.

Results and Analysis

The average student respondents were mostly college students, below twenty years old, and sixty-one percent (ninety-five cases) are females. The participants mostly spent an average of more than six hours online.

Table 1. Mean score for bullying level

Demographic Profile	Variable	Mean Score
Gender	Male	1.50
	Female	1.43
	Average	1.46
Age	Above 20	1.50
	Below 20	1.43
	Average	1.46
Type of Student	College	1.44
	Senior High School	1.49
	Average	1.46
No. of Hours Spent Online	More than 6 hours	1.44
	5 to 6 hours	1.53
	4 to 5 hours	1.33
	3 to 4 hours	1.52
	2 to 3 hours	1.48
	1 to 2 hours	1.64
	Average	1.46

Table 1 shows that there is a gradual increase in the participation of students in cyberbullying as they spent more time online. It is found that male respondents are slightly more involve in cyberbullying and people who spend more time in social media are more involved in cyberbullying compared to people who spends less than two hours per day. College and senior high school students regardless of being below or above twenty years old are all fairly involved in cyberbullying.

Table 2. Test of significant difference

Factor	P-value	Significance	H₀ Decision
Gender	0.300	Not Significant	Accept
Age	0.261	Not Significant	Accept
Type of Student	0.530	Not Significant	Accept
No. of Hours Spent	0.425	Not Significant	Accept

***Significant at .05 alpha level**

Table 2 shows that the researchers can accept the null hypothesis that students are involved in the participation of online bullying. Researchers have pointed out that among the under-age the use of social media is a commonplace. Thus, children and young people are using social media for longer periods of time and using multiple profiles across different social media platforms, as well as a connection between extensive use of social media with mental illness, gradual increase in cyberbullying cases especially online harassment, children and young people are vulnerable to the effects of cyberbullying as victims and perpetrators. There is a perceived lack of consequences for those who engaged in bullying behavior. The study supports this claim as the respondents are mostly below 20 years old, most spent a lot of time using social media. Along that direction, it clearly appears that all the participants used different social media platforms mostly Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram.

Discussion

Most of the students are college students and are below the age of 20. Most of the students are females. Most of the respondents spent more than six hours online mostly on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. There is also a trend towards the use of messaging apps such as Snapchat and Viber, and online forums such as Pinterest and Reddit. Bullying is a complex and relational issue, which has become increasingly complex as bullying behavior evolves online. We have found that cyberbullying takes different forms on different social media platforms.

The research also supports that contention that adolescents used social media in a very long period of time such as in a study done by Lenhart et al., (2005), where a sample of 1,100 students ages 12 to 17 years and their parents participated in a telephone survey to obtain data on adolescents' online habits in which it was found that 51% of the students used the Internet on a daily basis and 74% used instant messenger applications for up to 60 minutes per session (Mason, 2008). In another research by Ybarra and Mitchell (2004) found out that out of 1,498 adolescents ages 10 to 17 assessed, just about 24% sent hurtful material about another person, approximately 26% used chat rooms on a daily basis and approximately 25% used instant messaging daily. These studies validate the amount of time and convenience of access students have to electronic devices.

The results of the research show an average involvement among students in cyberbullying, of which, most students participated in online bullying especially students who spent more time on social media. It is safe to conclude that students have participated in cyberbullying across different social media platforms.

This study offers a series of achievable recommendations to ensure that children and adolescents understand their rights and responsibilities when using social media platforms, parents better understand how to help their children stay safe online, schools and universities equip students with knowledge of online safety and healthy relationships, government sets the right framework to ensure that there are minimum standards across platforms and social media companies take the lead, and show that they take their responsibilities towards their users seriously and make it easy for them to report bullying online.

References

- Calloway, C., & Paskewich, B. (2019, October 12). *Cyberbullying: Handling online conflict and aggression*. Children's Hospital of Philadelphia. https://www.chop.edu/news/health_tip/understanding-preventing-and-responding-bullying
- Holt, M. K., Vivolo-Kantor, A. M., Polanin, J. R., Holland, K. M., DeGue, S., Matjasko, J. L., Wolfe, M. & Reid, G. (2015). Bullying and suicidal ideation and behaviors: A meta-analysis. *Pediatrics*, 135(2), e496-e509. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2014-1864>
- Kemp, S. (2019). *Digital 2019: Essential insights into how people around the world use the internet, mobile devices, social media, and e-commerce*. Hootsuite. <https://p.widencdn.net/kqy7ii/Digital2019-Report-en>
- Lenhart, A., Madden, M., & Hitlin, P. (2005, July 27). *Teens and technology: You are leading the transition to a fully wired and mobile nation*. Pew Internet and American Life Project.

- Mason, K. L. (2008). Cyberbullying: A preliminary assessment for school personnel. *Psychology in the Schools, 45*(4), 323-348. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.20301>
- Moreno, M. A. (2014). Cyberbullying. *JAMA Pediatrics, 168*(5), 500. <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamapediatrics/article-abstract/1866047>
- Ybarra, M. L., & Mitchell, K. J. (2004). Online aggressor/targets, aggressors, and targets: A comparison of associated youth characteristics. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, 45*(7), 1308-1316. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2004.00328.x>
- Zuckerman, D. (2016). Bullying harms victims and perpetrators of all ages. *Health Progress, 97*(4), 63-66. <https://www.chausa.org/docs/default-source/health-progress/bullying-harms-victims-and-perpetrators-of-all-ages.pdf>